

PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMIC ACTIVITY OF YOUTH IN THE CONTEXT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CIVIL SOCIETY

Bakhtiyor Khamitovich Talipov

Senior Lecturer at the Fergana Branch

of TATU, Ph.D. in Philosophy

ORCID ID: 0009-0002-9430-746X

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15192969>

Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan, the deterministic foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition, and the prospects for the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition. The deterministic foundations of the development of youth economic activity in New Uzbekistan based on a culture of healthy competition are also analyzed.

Key words: youth economic activity, social laws, tradition and modernity, comparative analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic and functional, deterministic basis, culture of healthy competition.

Introduction. In the context of the development of civil society, great attention is being given to raising the spirituality of young people, increasing their socio-economic activity, and developing their aesthetic consciousness, worldview, and culture. This is not without reason. As it is stated, “a person has become the master of his own fate, responsible and accountable for social well-being, freedom, and creative labor, while also guaranteed political, economic, and spiritual freedom in their activities.” As a result, firstly, the relationship of young people to labor and the objects of labor has fundamentally changed; secondly, in the recent past, a mentality of private ownership, which had been completely alien to human nature, was established, and activism emerged; thirdly, in the process of economic activation, the private nature of labor, which forms the material basis for free entrepreneurship and initiative, has become more prominent; fourthly, small businesses and private entrepreneurship have gained a leading social status in our society.

Literature Review and Methods. The economic activity of young people is reflected in the scientific observations of F. Primov, Y. Ernazarova, Sh. Quvondiqov, J. Mavlyanov, and Sh. Azamatov. In the CIS countries, scholars such as G.P. Voshonova, G.S. Godzina, L.G. Golovach, V.Y. Savchenko, D. Sakhal, D.I. Kokurin, O.A. Latuxa, A.D. Sheremet, and Y.V. Sherbinina have conducted research. These scholars focused on the changes in socio-economic life after the

post-totalitarian regime, the processes of systemic transformation, the realization of human economic rights and freedoms in national contexts, the development of business and entrepreneurship, and the issues related to innovation in scientific, technical, and societal progress. The scientific theoretical and socio-philosophical conclusions, analysis methods, and sociometric observations of these scholars are important for our research as well. Among foreign scholars, E. Porter, E. Michael, K.Y. Totyev, A.Y. Yudanov, G.L. Azoyev, A.P. Gradov, M.V. Konotopov, R.A. Fatkhutdinov, and A.Y. Kibanov have studied issues related to the improvement of the competition process.

Results and Discussion.

In the modern era, the new measure of young people's economic activity should be defined by the concept of "innovative activity" at the regional level. This is because innovation improves the aesthetic aspects of economic activity, the working conditions, the information space of employment, and the developed aesthetic taste of producers. By classifying regions based on high, medium, and low levels of innovative activity, it is possible to identify "innovative attractors." Since the level of employment is the initial indicator of activity, the labor market is now directed towards innovation, focusing on talented youth and becoming unique centers, "growth poles," which are transforming into the "aesthetic substance" of development. In innovative centers, new forms of economic activity of young people and more effective labor practices develop, macro and micro-economic linkages become more apparent, and the number of innovative organizations improving personnel training and education increases.

Economic activity focuses on achieving efficiency, responding to modern technical, economic, and ethical requirements of products, meeting aesthetic needs, and the role of consumer culture formation is receiving significant attention. Naturally, this cannot be achieved without professional training, ideological-educational, aesthetic, and overall cultural competence.

Under the conditions of the development of an innovative economy, the correlation of aesthetic factors in the economic activity, activity, and striving for profit among young people is evident. These aesthetic factors perform several functions in activating the economic activity of young people. This relationship can be analyzed through the following methods of innovative technological approaches:

Empirical — acquiring knowledge through sensory perception. This technology focuses on improving the sensory-perceptual and aesthetic knowledge of young people based on their naturally developed sensory abilities.

Cognitive — expanding the aesthetic knowledge of the environment, the world, and people. This involves developing young people's thinking by analyzing aesthetic objects that cause emotional responses.

Heuristic — a method aimed at stimulating and motivating economic activity, improving economic thinking by choosing the most optimal options.

Creative — focusing on creativity, fostering useful and creative thinking directed towards "beauty creation" among young people.

Inversion — studying different parameters of aesthetic objects and replacing elements that provide aesthetic pleasure, thereby forming an economic-aesthetic thinking system.

Integrative — identifying a single correct conclusion based on the interconnectedness and unity of many small parts that make up aesthetic objects.

Adaptive — adapting the process of producing aesthetic knowledge to the development of the innovative economy and creating favorable conditions for learning and teaching.

Inclusive — forming consumer culture based on equality in the relationships between entrepreneurs and consumers.

In the activities of young people, entrepreneurship, business acumen, and the ability to express freedom of thought are increasingly integrating into the system of labor, behavior, life, and moral relationships, which are based on an aesthetic foundation in modern conditions. These show the social importance of aesthetic factors in elevating each individual's life activities and creative potential.

In the innovative economic system, the aesthetic development of young people establishes a humanistic relationship toward their work, social responsibility, and moral norms, transforming them into aesthetic beliefs. Their social significance leads to an increase in emotional and intellectual qualities, and creative potential is enhanced. Aesthetic development shapes an active life position and harmonizes the knowledge, behavior, emotions, and duties of an individual.

The result of economic activity, which leads to entrepreneurship, involves the process of producing material goods and aesthetically absorbing the outcomes. The progress of science and technology has necessitated ensuring

aesthetic conditions in the production processes. The aesthetics of entrepreneurship, as a specific form of material and artistic culture, is based on the laws of elegance. The aesthetics of entrepreneurship plays a vital role as an educational tool for the comprehensive development of human beings, forming part of society's spiritual culture. In entrepreneurial aesthetics, the entrepreneur's aesthetic consciousness, aesthetic perception process, relationship, activity, taste, understanding, aesthetic feeling, artistic taste, ideal, and aesthetic worldview are systematically analyzed. It is evident that entrepreneurship is a key element of aesthetic education, creating both material and spiritual beauty.

In general, under the conditions of innovative economic development, the aestheticization of the economy can be understood as follows:

Aestheticizing the economy on the basis of innovation to ensure the replacement of old generations of techniques and technologies in labor activities.

Adapting the design requirements of new techniques and technologies resulting from the innovative environment.

Developing new ideas, synthesizing new theories, and presenting them in innovative markets regarding the aestheticization of young people's economic activity.

Developing programs to aestheticize the economic activity of youth, adapting innovative aesthetic activity to economic demands.

The fusion of innovation and economic activity results in deeper and more active engagement with work, satisfaction, and creativity.

Based on the formation of a healthy aesthetic taste, young people strengthen their moral and creative potential, prioritize ethical-aesthetic norms in their relations with nature, society, family, and people, and increasingly materialize their ideas of beauty, resulting in the development of their spirituality and worldview.

A desire emerges among young people to integrate creativity into innovations in economic activity.

The aesthetic culture and creativity developed among modern youth significantly influence the formation of independent worldviews and free economic thinking.

Conclusion. Youth who understand their identity and strategic actions should not only be aware of the aesthetic principles of labor and ethics of their

people but also enrich them, applying them to production activities, and transforming them into a part of their aesthetic culture.

For increasing the economic activity of young people, the reorganization of local handicraft centers, the development of pottery and folk craftsmanship, and the organization of various events and even competitions are continuously being conducted. The development of national handicrafts, which is part of the ancient economic lifestyle of our people, plays a crucial role. Indeed, handicrafts are one of the key areas of our aesthetic culture.

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